

Correction Added to The Contemporary Formula of The Cosmological
Constant Problem

By

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Nomenclature:

$$c = \text{Speed of light} = 3E8 \frac{m}{s}$$

E = Energy associated with the wavelength of a Planck length

E_{pl-hyp} = The energy hypothesized to exist in the Planck volume in this report

G = Newtonian gravitational constant

h_r = Reduced Planck constant

l_{pl} = Planck length

ρ_{actual} = Actual value of vacuum energy density

ρ_{QM-hyp} = Hypothetical quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density

$\rho_{QM-current}$ = Contemporary current quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density

$vol.$ = Volume associated with the wavelength of the Planck length

Abstract:

In this report, a correction is added to the current equation for the cosmological constant problem. With this correction, it is concluded that the quantum mechanics value of energy density equals the actual value of energy density even though no value of energy density is calculated, thus, the cosmological constant problem is not truly solved in this report. This correction has to do with the fact that the volume associated with a wavelength of the Planck length is vastly larger than the Planck volume. The energy within the large volume of space that causes the wavelength of the Planck length is assumed to be the energy that exists within the Planck volume for the contemporary method of the cosmological constant problem, which may be incorrect.

The current contemporary formula for the value of the quantum mechanics vacuum energy density is written below:

$$\rho_{QM} = \frac{h_r * c}{l_{pl}^4} = \frac{h_r * c}{l_{pl}} \frac{1}{l_{pl}^3} = \frac{E}{l_{pl}^3} \quad (1)$$

The formula for the Planck length is written below:

$$l_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{h_r * G}{c^3}} \quad (2)$$

The formula for the energy associated with the wavelength of the Planck length is written below which uses the Planck-Einstein relation:

$$E = \rho_{actual} * vol. = \frac{h_r * c}{l_{pl}} \quad (3)$$

Next, after rearranging equation 3, the volume of space associated with the wavelength of the Planck length (which is vastly larger than the Planck volume) is written below:

$$vol. = \frac{h_r * c}{l_{pl} * \rho_{actual}} \quad (4)$$

The contemporary cosmological constant problem methodology concentrates the energy from the large volume associated with the wavelength of the Planck length to the volume of the Planck volume for its calculation of vacuum energy density, which may be incorrect. To get the actual energy density from the quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density, multiply this current contemporary quantum mechanics value by the ratio of the Planck volume to the volume associated with a wavelength of the Planck length, essentially undoing this concentration effect of these two volumes. This formula uses equation 4:

$$\rho_{actual} = \rho_{QM-current} * \frac{l_{pl}^3}{vol.} = \frac{h_r * c}{l_{pl}^4} \left(\frac{l_{pl}^3 * l_{pl} * \rho_{actual}}{h_r c} \right) = \rho_{QM-hyp} \quad (5)$$

With this correction:

$$\rho_{actual} = \rho_{actual} = \rho_{QM-hyp} \quad (6)$$

The equation below can also be written using equation 1:

$$\rho_{QM-hyp} = \frac{E_{pl-hyp}}{l_{pl}^3} = \frac{\rho_{actual} * l_{pl}^3}{l_{pl}^3} = \rho_{actual} \quad (7)$$

While quantum mechanics may not be able to calculate the actual vacuum energy density without data of the cosmos, such as the frequency associated with the energy density, it can be confirmed that the quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density equals the actual energy density with the correction applied.